

Some aspects of pattern formation during electrochemical deposition of metals[†]

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Electrochemical deposition is a typical example of far from equilibrium growth phenomena^{1,2}. Irreversible aggregation of small particles to form large clusters are technologically and scientifically important³⁻⁷. The formation of patterns and shapes of chemical and biological systems have considerable interest. The study of morphological stability of growing bodies, crystal growth, development of chemical waves and rhythmic crystallization in gel media offers one possibility for investigating non-equilibrium structures in physicochemical and biological systems⁸. One can explore a wide variety of morphologies during electrochemical deposition⁹⁻¹⁴ by varying the experimental conditions.

Much attention was given recently to the deposition of aggregates from a solution of a salt of metal without a supporting electrolyte¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Electrochemical deposition of ramified metallic clusters in thin cells, without supporting electrolyte has attracted much attention during the last decade because of its possible relationship with the diffusion-limited aggregation (DLA) algorithm proposed by Witten and Sander^{19,20}.

As compared to other growing phenomena, electro-deposition offers an unique opportunity to show very different morphologies from largely disordered fractal to well ordered anisotropic dendritic structure^{21,22}. Morphology transitions are very similar to those obtained in different physical or biological systems.

The feasibility of cathodic electrolytic deposition of various ceramic materials has recently been demonstrated including individual oxides and hydroxides, complex oxide compounds and composites. This method offers important advantages²³ and holds promise for various applications. Cathodic electrodeposition is achieved via hydrolysis of metal ions or complexes by electrogenerated base to form oxide, hydroxide or peroxide deposits on cathodic substrates; hydroxide and peroxide deposits can be converted to the corresponding oxides by thermal treatment. Electrodeposition of yttrium oxide films as well as complex oxide films containing yttrium oxide is of considerable interest for electrochemical and electronic applications²⁴⁻²⁶.

Electrochemical deposition consists of growing of a metallic cluster in an electrochemical cell filled with a solution of a salt of the metal, by imposing a constant current, or potential difference between the electrodes. At the cathode, the reaction is

where M is the metallic ion and Z is charge at metallic ion and e^- is the electron.

Electrodeposition is an important industrial process. It provides a wide variety of control parameters. Major factors influencing the appearance of the electrodeposited metal are : current density, concentration of electrolyte, viscosity, temperature, presence of colloidal particles, nature of electrolyte and geometry. A fascinating example of electrodeposition is the coloring titanium and related metals by electrochemical oxidation²⁷. Using a common d.c. power supply with current-limiting capabilities one can obtain a wide range of oxide layers on the surface of a metal by simply varying the applied voltage. For example, titanium metal is colored purple at 15 V and bronze at 50 V.

In view of the industrial and other applications of electrodeposition and morphology of electrodeposited aggregates, exhaustive studies on a number of metals have been made by different workers.

One component systems

Matsushita *et al.*²⁸ described another example of fractal geometry exhibited by zinc by electrodeposition. In his experiment metallic zinc in the form known as zinc metal leaves was grown two-dimensionally. The experimental procedure used to grow zinc metal leaves involves an experimental setup as shown in Fig. 1. A glass vessel (dia. 20 cm × depth 10 cm) was filled with 2 M ZnSO₄ aqueous solution (4 mm depth) on to which butyl acetate was floated to make an interface. Tip of a carbon cathode, polished carefully, was then put at the centre so that the tip remained just on the surface.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup for the electrodeposition of metals (Ref 28).

The electrodeposition was initiated by applying a d.c. voltage between the carbon cathode and zinc ring plate anode. A zinc metal leaf grows two-dimensionally at the interface between the two liquids from the edge of the flat tip of the cathode towards the outside anode with an intricately branched random pattern. A typical fractal example of the zinc metal leaves is shown in Fig. 2. The growth of the deposit was recorded with a camera and then processed by image analysis technique. The fractal dimension was found to be $D = 1.66 \pm 0.03$, in excellent agreement with that of two-dimensional DLA patterns.

Pattern formation in the electrodeposition of Zn from a thin layer of $ZnSO_4$ solution was studied by Sawada *et al.*²⁹. The authors showed that dendrites and several distinct

Fig. 2. A typical example of a zinc metal leaf

disordered patterns could be realized simply by change of parameters. Most strikingly, a transition from dendritic crystals to disordered ramified patterns was found when the electrolyte concentration was reduced. The disordered

patterns might be described as fractal below a concentration-dependent cut-off length.

Thin layer electrodeposition of zinc :

Thin layer electrodeposition of metals has been fascinating for the last decade. Kuhn and Argoul³⁰ described an experiment for the determination of ionic mobilities by thin layer electrodeposition. They observed that the addition of small quantities of either Li_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 or Na_2SO_4 caused highly disordered structures. They also estimated the cationic mobilities and the values were found to be 4.3×10^{-4} , 6.2×10^{-4} , $9.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ , respectively. However, the experimental values were found to be considerably high comparable to the theoretical values. Sagues *et al.*³¹ reported the basic concepts of fractal geometry and applied to quasi-two-dimensional zinc electrodeposits.

The quasi-two-dimensional electrochemical deposition process provides us with a great variety of structures whose morphologies depend on the experimental conditions. In the special case of zinc aggregates formed from an aqueous solution of zinc sulfate, a transition from anisotropic and dendrite-like patterns to more disordered structures such as open fractal and homogeneous deposits, is observed when electrolyte concentration and applied potential are changed during experiments. Morphological diagram for zinc electrodeposition is shown in Fig. 3. At low potential value, open zinc electrodeposits are formed showing their characteristic tip-splitting of the branches. The structures are similar to those obtained using DLA algorithm in computer simulations and can be characterized in terms of fractal geometry.

Experimental results on electrodeposit patterns of $CuSO_4$ solution was presented in both radial and long cells. The solution was placed (i) between two plastic blocks (closed cell) or (ii) in a dish open to air (open cell). Copper electrodes and three types of cells were employed. These include (i) open cells-circular anode, (ii) closed cells-circular anode, and (iii) closed cells-parallel electrodes.

Kozhanov *et al.*³² used SEM to study the effect of time (25–180 min) on the morphology of electrodeposited Cu at super high c.d. $\approx 300 \text{ A m}^{-2}$. The morphology of Cu deposit is characterized by clusters and microdendrites at 30–40 min deposition time. The formation of spheroids and the increase of their size was determined at a deposition time >40 min. The stratification of the electrolyte enhanced the compact spheroid formation.

Fleury *et al.*³³ reported the growth speed of metal electrodepositions in case of electrodeposition without

Fig. 3. Electrolyte concentration versus applied potential with respect to the morphologies of zinc electrodeposition (adopted from Ref. 31).

supporting electrolyte, and performed electrodeposition experiments in parallel geometry under galvanostatic conditions, i.e. with a constant current. In case of potentiostatic conditions, the deposits generally exhibited a fractal morphology at a low applied potential and dense-parallel branching morphology at higher voltages. The authors observed a similar classification in galvanostatic conditions and focused the attention on growths exhibiting dense-parallel morphology, which were obtained at relatively high current densities.

Fleury *et al.*³⁴ studied the growth of electrodeposits from solutions of copper sulfate in thin cells, and focussed our attention on the spectacular morphological transitions that occur in almost every experimental condition. The authors gave experimental evidence and numerical and theoretical results showing that these transitions were due to the propagation of charged impurities leaving the dissolving anode at the beginning of the growth and hitting the deposit at later times. In case of usual experiment, with a copper anode and a copper cathode, the scaling of the transition line can be demonstrated by taking several rectangular cells of different widths where the transition occurs.

Fleury *et al.*³⁵ reported an extensive study of electrochemical deposition of copper with growth under

galvanostatic conditions and parallel geometry. In such conditions a clear understanding of the origin of the ramified deposit and of its growth speed is possible, at least in the case of dense morphology. They confirmed that this morphology belonged to a steady-state regime where growth could be modeled as the displacement of a flat strip of nearly equipotential copper. The growth velocity is exactly the drift velocity of the anions, which is proportional to the current density. The authors showed that the mass of the deposit did not depend on the speed at which it was grown. Ross *et al.*³⁶ investigated electrodeposition of copper from CuSO_4 solutions under high electric field and gives rise to ramified deposits. They have studied electrodeposition of copper from copper sulfate in thin rectangular cells with thickness 0.3 or 0.5 mm. For the study in a gel, a 2% agar agar solution was prepared in hot water.

Trigueros *et al.*³⁷ studied the influence of an inert electrolyte Na_2SO_4 on quasi-two-dimensional copper electrodeposition from aqueous copper sulfate solution. The influence of inert electrolyte was analyzed by representing a diagram of different deposit morphologies. Fig. 4 shows

Fig. 4. Diagram of morphologies for copper electrodeposition from a 0.05 M copper sulfate aqueous solution containing sodium sulfate (Ref. 37).

the plots of sodium sulfate concentration versus applied potential values while fixing the concentration of copper sulfate at 0.05 M. At higher inert electrolyte concentration and applied potential, the first structure of the deposit is the finger pattern like homogeneous patterns. The number of fingers increases with the inert electrolyte concentration and the applied potential. The morphology of the copper electrodeposit was clearly influenced by the presence of an inert electrolyte (sodium sulfate) in the solution.

Apart from the morphological changes of the deposit after small addition of inert electrolyte, the most interesting

feature was the finger-like morphology observed at higher applied potential and inert electrolyte concentrations. The growth velocity measurements of homogeneous patterns in the presence of an inert electrolyte in solution satisfactorily agreed with a theoretical model based on a migration transport regime of electroactive species from the bulk solution to the electrode surface. Growth velocities are linear with respect to inert electrolyte concentration mainly at low values, except when open fractal structures are formed; in this case, the growth velocity was clearly smaller than the calculated one from this model. At higher inert electrolyte concentrations, the measured growth velocities were smaller than the theoretical one.

Schilardi *et al.*³⁸ reported 2D copper branched aggregates grown from the electrodeposition of Cu^{II} ions on a small cathode in a 2D-electrochemical cell with a concentric anode-cathode arrangement at different applied voltages (ΔE). As ΔE was increased, the number of branches in the aggregates increased leading to nearly isotropic patterns. The fractal characterization of the isotropic electrodeposits was also made. The analysis of aggregate patterns and the radial velocity dependence on ΔE indicated that the growth of large branches was mainly controlled by the electric field between the cathode and the anode whereas small branches grown under diffusion.

Marshal *et al.*³⁹ made an effort to construct a macroscopic model for the description of growth pattern formation in copper electrodeposits. The theoretical model was formulated as a Stefan-like problem consisting in the Nernst-Planck equations. The proposed model was able to describe from fractal to dense branch morphology and in particular the interplay of the electroconvective, migration and diffusive motion of the ions near the growing tips. The comparison between computational and experimental deposits was limited by the 2D assumptions.

Cachet *et al.*⁴⁰ reported impedance measurements and SEM examination of deposits and showed that the mechanism of Zn deposition in Zincate alkaline electrolytes is highly sensitive to the electrolyte content in anodically dissolved Zn (i.e. ADZ). The nucleation and initial crystal growth kinetics of Zn electrodeposited from acidic Zn solutions was also studied in the absence or presence of Sb and glue on a glassy C-electrode.

Argoul *et al.*⁴¹ reported experimental evidences indicating that two-dimensional zinc electrodeposition clusters in the limit of small ionic concentration and small voltage are self-similar with generalized dimensions $D = 1.66 \pm 0.08$. The result suggested that electrodeposition and

diffusion-limited clusters have a similar geometrical structure.

Sawada *et al.*⁴⁷ reported the structure and growth velocity of electrochemical deposits grown from one-dimensional seeds as a function of electrolyte concentration. The growth velocity of zinc metal leaves was found to be independent of the concentration of zinc ions for a fixed potential of 15 V. In the concentration range 0.003–0.008 mol dm^{-3} , the local structure remains fractal, but the width of trees and the separation between the trees depend strongly on the concentration. The local structure suddenly changes from fractal to dendritic structure with backbones as 0.020 mol dm^{-3} . The discrepancy between the experimental results and the velocity selection mechanism based on DLA was reported.

Results showed that they were fractal up to some scale length and homogeneous above it. The spacing between the trees were widely separated when the concentration was extremely low but were reduced with increasing concentration. The growth velocity for each concentration remained fixed except for a short duration. The growth velocity was found to depend only weakly on the concentration. A systematic experimental study of quasi-two-dimensional zinc electrodeposition in an electrochemical cell with parallel electrodes was reported by Trigueros *et al.*⁴³. The well known different growth regimes from anisotropically dendritic to irregularly disordered fractal, described previously in radial cells, are shown together with a novel mixed structure composed of dendritic backbones with ramified open branches. Experiments conducted by varying the cell thickness and electrode separation show significant effects by the current on the pattern morphology. Finally, the self-similarity of the electrodeposits is examined for two different growth regimes. At higher applied potentials, a novel complex pattern was observed showing both open and dendrite characteristics. The growth initially was open but after some development, some trees were taken on a dendritic structure displaying a directional backbone and uniformly spaced lateral branches.

Several conclusions could be drawn from the experiments of Trigueros *et al.* The various morphologies observed could be classified into distinct growth regimes : (a) compact deposits are obtained at low potentials, (b) ramified structures with a well defined outer front, the so called dense branching appear at low concentrations over a wide range of applied potentials, (c) at higher concentrations, a limited region of dendritic growth is exhibited, (d) open ramified, fractal like deposits, (e) mixed structures with characteristics

of dendritic backbones. Some specific effects of cell dimensions on the morphology of zinc electrodeposits in a parallel cell are reported by Trigueros *et al.*⁴⁴. At high concentration values, a transition from mixed to string-like structure is observed as cell thickness is increased. Homogeneous patterns, which are observed at low concentration values, seem to be the most stable against modification of cell parameters.

Sagues *et al.*⁴⁴ also described experimental results to clarify pattern morphologies for quasi-two-dimensional Zn electrodeposits in a parallel cell. Two points were considered with regards to the morphology of zinc electrodeposition. First its dependence on concentration and applied potential and afterwards its dependence on cell dimensions. Results showed that deposit morphology strongly depended on potential and concentration values. Morphological diagram for various dimensions showed some differences at high concentration due to change in cell geometry. At high concentration, a transition from mixed to thicker and non-ramified stringy patterns was observed as cell thickness was increased.

Trigueros *et al.*⁴⁵ reported theoretical models for the study of electrode processes under diffusion-control on rough surfaces tested using quasi-two-dimensional experimental electrodes obtained by zinc electrodeposition. Exponent of a generalized scaling law similar to the classical Cottrell equation, was calculated using Monte Carlo simulation. The validity of the algorithms of the simulation was tested on flat electrodes. The shape of the electrode surface had an important role in the time-dependence of response functions of electrode processes. Two limiting cases were considered by the authors, flat and rough electrodes. Fractal terms were used for a geometrical characterization of rough, porous or partially active electrodes. Tomas *et al.*⁴⁶ described experimental procedure to grow quasi-two-dimensional zinc electrodeposits under forced convection conditions.

Pletcher *et al.*^{47,48} reported the electrodeposition of rhodium metal from 1 M NaCl + HCl, pH 1.5–4 and sulfate acidic media. The electrodeposition of palladium from an ammonia-free electrolyte with both direct current and pulse current was reported by Lai *et al.*⁴⁹. The polarization experiments showed that the electrode reactions included oxygen reduction, hydrogen evolution and palladium deposition. The oxygen reduction was always mass transfer controlled. Deposit obtained with current densities higher than the limiting one was powdery. The current efficiency also dropped under these condition.

Ring morphology in interfacial electrodeposition of silver

was reported by Zeiri *et al.*⁵⁰. Silver electrodeposition at the air/water interface yielded a unreported ring morphology. This was attributed to oscillatory accumulation/detachment cycles of hydrogen at the growing edge of the deposit. With this morphology, the measured morphological diagram closely resembles that of bacterial colony growth indicating a similarity of the underlying growth mechanism.

Fractal surfaces of gold and platinum electrodeposits :

The fractal nature of the surfaces of thin films was studied. Gomez-Rodriguez *et al.*⁵¹ reported the structure of gold and platinum deposits grown on gold and platinum wire cathodes, respectively, by electroreduction of the corresponding oxide layers and analyzed in terms of surface fractals by measuring the perimeter L and area A of intergranular voids. Perimeter and area were determined from scanning tunneling microscopy (STM).

Pattern formation during electrodeposition of lead metal :

Pattern formation and growth behavior during electrochemical deposition of lead from its aqueous solution was studied by Rastogi *et al.*⁵² using two platinum electrodes placed horizontally. Cathode potential changes with time during the process of electrodeposition of lead metal in batch reactor as well as in a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) were studied. Growth kinetics at constant current/potential were studied for correlation.

Influence of electrolyte concentration, applied current and certain polymer additives such as PVA and agar agar on morphologies, growth kinetics and oscillatory characteristics were reported. Experimental results indicated that the morphology changed on addition of minute quantities of these polymer additives. The dendritic growth was observed when aqueous lead acetate was used whereas a DLA/fractal type structure was observed when PVA was added in the solution.

The cathodic electrolytic deposition of various complex oxide offers important advantages for electrochemical and various electronic applications. Recently some work on yttrium oxide and morphology of electrodeposited WO_3 have been reported^{53,54}. Thin film of yttrium oxide were obtained from aqueous $\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and YCl_3 salt solutions via cathodic electrodeposition. The electrodeposition yield was studied under various experimental conditions. By varying the current density, deposition time and electrolyte concentration and the amount of the deposited material could be controlled. The deposits were studied by X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetric analysis and scanning electron microscopy.

Formation of crystalline yttrium oxide from the hydroxide precursor was observed at 600°.

Two component systems

New results on the non-equilibrium growth patterns of silver were reported by Das *et al.*⁵⁵ in a batch reactor using cells with different electroodic arrangements. Electrodeposition experiments were carried out employing (i) two parallel electrodes and (ii) a point cathode and a circular anode. The fractal dimension D of the electrodeposited cluster of silver obtained with an experimental setup consisting of circular anode and point cathode was found to be 1.95. The value was slightly higher than that for 2-dimensional diffusion limited aggregation (DLA) model. On addition of another metal electrolyte (copper nitrate), a transition from fractal to more dense branched morphology (the so called Hecker's effect) occurred. Cathode potential changes with time were monitored in batch and flow reactors, and oscillations of small amplitude observed. Next area plots indicated that oscillations were periodic.

Milchev *et al.*⁵⁶ reported the results of a galvanostatic study of the growth kinetics of single metal and alloy clusters electrochemically deposited on a platinum electrode. Information is obtained on the growth rate in one- and two-component electrochemical systems, containing Ag^+ and $\text{Ag}^+ + \text{Hg}_2^{2+}$ ions, respectively. In both cases KNO_3 was used as a supporting electrolyte. The results provide detailed information on the growth kinetics of silver and silver/mercury alloy clusters under galvanostatic conditions.

Emm *et al.*⁸⁶ reported a relation between electrolytic activity for the hydrogen evolution reaction and the surface component of the electrode established for Ni-Zr crystal and amorphous alloys by secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS). Electrocatalytic activity was tested by cathodic polarization in 1 M KOH at 25° and the resulting exchange current density was taken as a measure of catalytic efficiency. The consequent morphology and compositional surface changes were studied by DSC, XRD and SEM. The electrochemical behavior of pure elements (Ni and Zr) was also considered for comparison.

Masao *et al.*⁵⁸ reported novel Ni-Sn alloy cathodes with high catalytic activity developed. Characteristics and catalytic ability of electrodeposited nickel-tin alloy as a hydrogen evolution cathode was strongly dependent on preparation condition.

A rotating electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance was designed and used to study the electrodeposition of copper-selenium compounds on the gold from an aqueous solution of CuSO_4 and H_2SeO_3 reported by Morlot *et al.*⁵⁹.

Thin film was prepared over a range of potential and precursor concens in the deposition bath. The composition of the films was determined by simultaneous measurements of the quantity of charge and gains in the mass.

The composition surface morphology and appearance of Zn-Co alloy deposits as a function of current density, electrode potential and Co^{2+} concentration in the electrolyte were studied by Kirilova *et al.*⁶⁰. The potentiodynamic dissolution of coatings with Co content of 6.54 indicates successive deposition of Co-enriched phases and a pure Zn phase. The Zn-Co alloys were found to be more corrosion resistant than zinc but less resistant than cobalt.

Electrodeposition and dissolution of Co-W alloy films were studied by Aravindo *et al.*⁶¹. The observed cyclic voltammetric data showed that the alloy deposition was possibly from cobalt-tungstate complex. The citrate ions and DMSO hinder the alloy deposition. DMSO which specifically adsorbs on the electrode surface, favors the H evolution reaction (HER) whereas tungstate hinders the HER. Stripping voltammograms show the existence of cobalt-rich alloy phases. X-Ray diffraction study further confirmed the phases to be Co_3W and Co_7W .

Bismuth telluride alloy films of uniform thickness were prepared by Magri *et al.*⁶² by electrodeposition from a solution containing Bi^{3+} and HTeO_2^+ ions in 1 mol dm^{-3} nitric acid on stainless steel. The electrodeposited films were monophasic and exhibited a polycrystalline structure. The film composition was dependent on the electrolyte composition and the current density. The electrical properties of the electrodeposited samples were determined. The obtained films were n -type semiconductors, with high carrier concentration.

Electrodeposition techniques have been successfully employed for the preparation of chalcogenide semiconductors, e.g. CdS, CdSe, CdTe, InSe, PbTe with regard to bismuth chalcogenide; thin films of the sulfide were prepared by anodization of bismuth metal in polysulfide solutions and by direct electrodeposition from non-aqueous media. The synthesis of electrodeposited bismuth telluride films is based on the electroreduction of telluride ions, in the presence of bismuth salts.

Das *et al.*⁶³ reported experimental results on fractal growth and oscillations during electrochemical deposition in Pb-Zn binary system. Growth kinetics data for different electrode systems were compared. The data obey the simple empirical equation, $d = ct^m$, where d is the radius of the circular envelope grown in time t . Scanned pictures of electrodeposits have been characterized in terms of fractal

dimension by box counting method. The values of D were in good agreement with the values of diffusion limited aggregation clusters. Cathode potential changes with time was also monitored during the process of electrodeposition and dissolution. Next amplitude plots indicated that the oscillations were periodic in the binary system while for pure Pb and Zn it was like random noise.

2D-electrodeposits from aqueous solutions of copper sulfate, zinc sulfate and mixture of copper sulfate-zinc sulfate in different proportions were investigated by Das *et al.*^{64a}. Morphology of deposits from $\text{CuSO}_4 + \text{ZnSO}_4$ solutions showed mixed cauliflower structure and dendritic structure characteristic of copper and zinc, respectively. The results showed that deposits are not homogeneous. Growth kinetic studies and cathode potential changes during electrodeposition indicated approximately regular behavior during the growth of electrodeposit.

2D-branched aggregates of a two-component system (Fig. 5) containing Cu and Al were grown by Das *et al.*^{64b}

Fig. 5. Electrodeposited aggregate obtained from a mixture of aqueous solutions of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ at the field intensity 2.40 V/cm (adopted from Ref. 63).

(Fig. 6). Different electrode setups were employed. Aggregates were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). Fractal dimension D was found to be much higher than that of pure Cu. Growth rates were also measured at different experimental conditions.

Fig. 6. Electrodeposited aggregate obtained from a mixture of aqueous solutions of CuSO_4 and AlCl_3 when a current of 60 mA was applied across the electrodes for 10 min (adopted from Ref. 64b).

Three and four component systems

Lead and tin based alloys are widely used as engineering materials in bush bearing applications. Recently, microstructural features induced by spray forming of a ternary Pb-Sn-Sb alloy have been reported by Srivastava *et al.*⁶⁵. An alloy containing Pb 12%, Sn 12%, Sb with small addition of copper and arsenic was spray-deposited employing two different atomization gas pressure and nozzle to substrate distances. The temperature of the spray-deposit was measured during deposition at a distance of 2–10 mm above the substrate-deposit interface. Thermal profile data indicated small variation in temperature with time during deposition stage, whereas during post-deposition stage an exponential decrease in temperature was recorded second phase particle size along the thickness of the deposit varied from 4 to 8 μm compared to 70 to 80 μm size of these particles in the cast alloy. Maximum porosity occurred in the section of the deposit near the contact surface of the substrate and also in its peripheral regions. X-Ray diffraction analysis exhibited the formation of additional Cu_2Sb phase in the spray-deposit and CuSn and Cu_{33}Sb phases in atomized powders compared to that of the cast alloy.

Quaternary mixed chalcopyrites are of special interest because they offer the possibility of tailoring the reflective index, band gap and lattice parameters via the film composition. Cu-In-Se-Te thin films have been produced by electrodeposition on molybdenum electrodes supported

on glass substrate⁶⁶. The composition of the films is a function of the growth conditions.

The best conditions for a near-stoichiometric composition was the deposition potential of -0.5 V vs SCE and a time greater than 4000 s. After electrodeposition the samples became amorphous. However, crystallization of the films could be achieved by various thermal treatments, for example, annealing in a Te atmosphere at 550° for 30 min followed by annealing under vacuum at 400° for 1 h. This produced crystalline quaternary phases, as confirmed by X-ray diffraction studied. The same films exhibited photoelectrochemical responses with flat band potentials of -0.15 V. All samples exhibited *p*-type conduction.

The Bi(Pb)-Sr-Ca-CuO high-*T_c* cuprates with a normal stoichiometry of $(\text{BiPb})_2\text{-Sr}_2\text{-Ca}_2\text{-Cu}_3\text{O}$ were considered to be the most promising superconducting materials for practical applications. Desai *et al.*⁶⁷ have recently reported superconducting thin films of Bi(Pb)-Sr-Ca-CuO (BSCCO) system and prepared by depositing the film onto silver substrate by d.c. electrodeposition technique with dimethyl sulfoxide bath in order to examine the effect of Pb addition to the BSCCO system. The films were deposited at the potential of -0.8 V vs saturated calomel electrode (SCE) onto the silver substrate. The different preparative parameters such as deposition potential, deposition time were studied and optimized. These films were then oxidized electrochemically at room temperature in an alkaline (1 N KOH) solution, and also at 600° temperature in an oxygen atmosphere. The film showed superconducting behavior. To obtain Bi-Pb-Sr-Ca-Cu-alloyed films with required stoichiometry of 2 : 2 : 2 : 3, the total bath composition was adjusted by considering the rate of deposition of each of its constituents. The film showed the superconducting behavior with *T_c* values. The authors strongly recommend using the room temperature electrochemical oxidation technique to obtain stable Bi 2223-thin films.

Photochemical deposition :

Recently Goto *et al.*⁶⁸ have developed a new technique called photochemical deposition (PCD). Photochemical deposition is emerging as a new and simple technique to deposit thin films. Compared to other techniques, the PCD is a most convenient method. PCD technique is developed and applied to both sulfide and selenide semiconductors.

CdS is widely used for a window layer of CdTe or CuInSe_2 based solar cells. Cadmium sulfide thin films are deposited using PCD techniques. The growth solution contains mixture of cadmium sulfate and sodium thiosulfate. The films are deposited at different pHs and different concentrations. A glass substrate was dipped in growth

solution and illuminated by UV-lamp through spherical simple lens. The cadmium sulfide film was formed only in the illuminated region. Absorption spectra of the aqueous solution were taken before and after illumination. There was a variation in the absorption edge. The CdS thin film was characterized by XRD and SEM. The lattice parameters are in good agreement with ASTM.

Electrochemical oscillations

In recent years, there has been a tremendous increase in the number of experimental and theoretical studies of oscillations and spatial pattern formation. Such systems can be designated as oscillatory in the sense that repeated maxima and minima in the value of some property can occur in time or space. Oscillations occur only when the system is far away from thermodynamic equilibrium achieved by imposing some sort of external force, such as concentration gradient electrical field, imposed light and others. Many examples of biochemical and cellular oscillations are known and have been extensively studied. Systematic studies on sustained potential oscillations in an artificial membrane was carried out by Teorell, who discussed the possible physicochemical model for the action potential in neurons.

Suter and Wong⁶⁹ reported periodic oscillations with constant applied voltage (current) during electrochemical growth of zinc dendrites. Oscillations were observed due to the side-branching nature of dendrites. The authors find that whenever dendrites are formed, the cell current (*I*) exhibits periodic oscillations even though the applied voltage (*V*) is held constant. Similarly, *V* oscillates when a constant *I* is applied. For increasing orderliness of the dendrites, the magnitude of oscillation is larger (up to 10% of the average signal) and the coherence time is longer (up to several minutes). There are no oscillations at low current density. The oscillations must be associated with a deposition reaction at high current density.

Argoul *et al.*⁷⁰ reported a spatio temporal chaos in diffusion limited growth phenomena. They have explored a wide variety of morphologies, namely, dendritic, hybrid DLA and DLA-like fractal patterns during electrodeposition of zinc metal. The results suggest that electrodeposition and diffusion-limited clusters have a similar geometrical structure.

The morphology and cathode potential changes during electrochemical deposition under different experimental conditions in a batch reactors as well as in continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) have been reported by Rastogi *et al.*⁵². The experimental setup was employed to monitor the potential changes at the cathode during electrochemical deposition of lead metal at an air-water interface.

It has been observed that polymer additives influence the oscillatory and growth behavior during electrochemical deposition of the metal. It was found that amplitude decreases by adding an additive. The change may be ascribed as due to an appreciable increase in viscosity of the solution by adding a polymer material. In the case of CSTR, fluctuations were periodic, whereas in a batch reactor, oscillations were more like random noise. The potential changes with time during electrochemical deposition of lead from its aqueous solutions of different concentrations ranging from dilute solution (0.1 M) to saturated solutions and keeping the current across the electrodes constant (4.0 mA). It was observed that cathode potential oscillates with time but no such oscillation could be observed when saturated solution was used, indicating that at high concentration, dendritic growth is more controlled and hence potential does not fluctuate.

Non-equilibrium growth patterns of silver and oscillations during electrodeposition of metals in batch and flow reactors were reported by Das *et al.*⁵⁵. Cathode potential changes with time were monitored and oscillations of small amplitude observed. Next area plots indicate that oscillations are periodic.

Techniques employed in characterization of electrodeposited materials :

The electrodeposited aggregates are characterized by different techniques. These include : atomic force microscopy (AFM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), scanning tunneling microscopy (STM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), electron probe microanalysis (EPM), electron spectroscopy for chemical analysis (ESCA), ion-scattering spectroscopy (ISS), auger electron spectroscopy (AES), X-ray emission spectroscopy, ion-emission microscopy, IR and ESR study etc.

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